

Mars Sample Return Using Commercial Capabilities: Mission Architecture Overview

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Abstract— Mars Sample Return (MSR) is the highest priority science mission for the next decade as recommended by the recent Decadal Survey of Planetary Science. This paper presents an overview of a feasibility study for a MSR mission. The objective of the study was to determine whether emerging commercial capabilities can be used to reduce the number of mission systems and launches required to return the samples, with the goal of reducing mission cost. The major elements required for the MSR mission are described and include an integration of the emerging commercial capabilities with small spacecraft design techniques; new utilizations of traditional aerospace technologies; and recent technological developments.

We report the feasibility of a complete and closed MSR mission design using the following scenario that can start in any one of three Earth to Mars launch opportunities, beginning in 2022: A Falcon Heavy injects a SpaceX Red Dragon capsule and trunk onto a Trans Mars Injection (TMI) trajectory. The capsule is modified to carry all the hardware needed to return samples collected on Mars including a Mars Ascent Vehicle (MAV); an Earth Return Vehicle (ERV); and hardware to transfer a sample collected in a previously landed rover mission, such as the Mars 2020 rover, to the ERV. The Red Dragon descends to land on the surface of Mars using Supersonic Retro Propulsion (SRP). After previously collected samples are transferred to the ERV, the single-stage MAV launches the ERV from the surface of Mars to a Mars phasing orbit. The MAV uses a storable liquid, pump-fed bi-propellant propulsion system. After a brief phasing period, the ERV, which also uses a storable bi-propellant system, performs a Trans Earth Injection (TEI) burn. Once near Earth the ERV

performs Earth and lunar swing-bys and is placed into a Lunar Trailing Orbit (LTO)- an Earth orbit, at lunar distance. A later mission, using a Dragon and launched by a Falcon Heavy, performs a rendezvous with the ERV in the lunar trailing orbit, retrieves the sample container and breaks the chain of contact with Mars by transferring the sample into a sterile and secure container. With the sample contained, the retrieving spacecraft, makes a controlled Earth re-entry preventing any unintended release of pristine Martian materials into the Earth's biosphere. Other capsule type vehicles and associated launchers may be applicable. An MSR launch in 2022 becomes the preferred option if the Mars 2020 rover is the previous sample caching vehicle.

The analysis methods employed standard and specialized aerospace engineering tools. Mission system elements were analyzed with either direct techniques or by using parametric mass estimating relationships (MERs). The architecture was iterated until overall mission convergence was achieved on at least one path. Subsystems analyzed in this study include support structures, power system, nose fairing, thermal insulation, actuation devices, MAV exhaust venting, and GN&C. Best practice application of loads, mass growth contingencies, and resource margins were used. For Falcon Heavy capabilities and Dragon subsystems we utilized publically available data from SpaceX; published analyses from other sources; as well as our own engineering and aerodynamic estimates.

Earth Launch mass is under 11 mt, which is within the estimated capability of a Falcon Heavy, with margin. Total entry masses between 7 and 10 mt were considered with

closure occurring between 9 and 10 mt. Propellant mass fractions for each major phase of the EDL - Entry, Terminal Descent, and Hazard Avoidance were derived. An assessment of the entry condition effects on the thermal protection system (TPS), currently in use for Dragon missions, showed no significant stressors. A useful mass of 2.0 mt is provided and includes mass growth allowances for the MAV, the ERV, and mission unique equipment.

We also report on alternate propellant options for the MAV and options for the ERV, including propulsion systems; crewed versus robotic retrieval mission; as well as direct Earth entry.

International Planetary Protection (PP) policies as well as verifiable means of compliance with both forward and back contamination controls, will have a large impact on any MSR mission design. We identify areas within our architecture where such impacts occur.

This work shows that emerging commercial capabilities can be effectively integrated into a mission to achieve an important planetary science objective.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION	2
2. MSR MISSION CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS	2
3. STUDY METHODOLOGY	3
4. ARCHITECTURE ELEMENT DESCRIPTION.....	4
5. PLANETARY PROTECTION POLICY	10
6. CONCLUSION AND MAJOR FINDINGS	11
7. FUTURE WORK	12
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND DISCLAIMER	13
REFERENCES.....	14
BIOGRAPHIES & CONTRIBUTIONS	15

1. INTRODUCTION

Mars Sample Return (MSR) has been identified as the highest priority planetary science mission for the next decade by the most recent version of the Decadal Survey of Planetary Science [1]. MSR has been the subject of several

studies within the last three decades [2 – 6]. Proposed missions resulting from those studies have been large, complex, and by extension, costly.

This paper provides an overview of the results of a study of a new MSR architecture. This new architecture leverages the use of emerging commercial capabilities in order to reduce the complexity and cost of previous approaches.

The objective of the study was to determine whether emerging commercial capabilities can be integrated into such a mission. The premises of the study is that commercial capabilities can be more efficient than previously described systems, and by using fewer systems and fewer or less extensive launches, overall mission cost can be reduced. The original sampling intent of the planetary science community is preserved in the new architecture. A key fact is that the Mars 2020 rover will be tasked with gathering and caching samples onboard for future retrieval.

This MSR architecture is technically feasible within any one of three consecutive Earth to Mars launch opportunities, beginning in 2022. The 2022 opportunity is the preferred option since the shortest mission extension, approximately 12 months, will be required for the 2020 rover. Such an extension will require a programmatic commitment to proceed with MSR at an early date. Mission extensions are recognized as difficult to justify in the current budget climate, however, the potential for emerging commercial capabilities as well as an architecture that is simpler than previous proposals, can offset this difficulty. The architecture covers a complete mission with all required elements and achieves mass closure.

2. MSR MISSION CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS

The MSR mission is illustrated in Figure 1 and begins with the launch of a SpaceX Falcon Heavy (FH) (currently under

Figure 1. Mars Sample Return Mission Architecture Diagram

development). The payload for the FH is a modified version of a SpaceX Dragon capsule, designated as “Red Dragon”, along with a trunk. The Red Dragon capsule is modified to carry all the hardware needed to return samples collected on Mars. These elements include a Mars Ascent Vehicle (MAV) and an Earth Return Vehicle (ERV). Also included are systems to support the MAV / ERV and the hardware needed to transfer a sample, collected and placed in a container by the 2020 rover mission, to the ERV. Red Dragon is sent on a Trans Mars Injection (TMI) trajectory by the FH upper stage. The mission continues with an interplanetary cruise of approximately 10 to 13 months, depending on opportunity. The launch and cruise operations are similar to traditional Mars missions.

Upon arrival at Mars, Red Dragon performs a direct entry followed by a non-traditional EDL using a lifting trajectory with bank angle modulation and Supersonic Retro Propulsion (SRP). Parachute braking or descent is not performed.

After previously collected samples are transferred to the ERV, the single-stage MAV launches the ERV from the surface of Mars to a short term phasing orbit. The MAV uses a storable liquid, pump-fed bi-propellant propulsion system. After the brief phasing period, the ERV, which also uses a storable bi-propellant system, performs a Trans Earth Injection (TEI) burn. The unique return interplanetary cruise towards Earth lasts approximately 10 to 12 months, depending on opportunity. Once near Earth the ERV performs Earth and lunar swing-bys and enters into a Lunar Trailing Orbit (LTO) – a high Earth orbit, at lunar distance and inclined to the plane of the Earth-moon system. A later mission, possibly using a capsule type vehicle such as Dragon, performs a rendezvous with the ERV in the LTO. The retrieval of the sample container from the ERV will be accomplished in a way that breaks the chain of contact with Mars by transferring the sample container into a suitably clean and secure container as required by COSPAR PP policy for Category V, restricted Earth return missions [7].

This retrieval option can also be performed with other combinations of capsule and launch vehicle. The mission can be either crewed or robotic. With the sample contained, the retrieving spacecraft makes a controlled Earth re-entry preventing any unintended release of pristine Martian materials into the Earth’s biosphere. The sample retrieving spacecraft will follow a course to the moon that is similar to an Apollo profile but will perform a lunar swing-by to match the ERV orbit. The return to Earth can either be performed propulsively, for a crewed case, or by another lunar swing-by in a robotic case.

A return option in which an Earth Entry Vehicle (EEV) performs an Earth Direct Entry (EDE) with the sample is also a possibility. This approach is similar to the one used in the MSR Orbiter Mission study 3 . The EEV in that study is too massive to fit within the architecture reported here. The application of advanced entry systems and Thermal Protection System, (TPS) technologies currently within

NASA’s portfolio, may provide sufficient mass reductions – provided that PP reliabilities can be achieved.

The direct Mars to Earth approach defines the key concept of this architecture. The Red Dragon enables the architecture by providing the required Mars landing capability. On the other hand the ERV balances the architecture by being the element that travels the furthest and carries the contained sample to Earth.

3. STUDY METHODOLOGY

To ensure feasibility, the MSR study team investigated a prioritized listing of elements to understand ramification of the architecture options. Trajectories detailing transit to Mars and back have been reconciled with Earth and Mars launch capabilities. These capabilities include an Earth launch vehicle under development, Falcon Heavy, as well as a custom designed MAV that utilizes design heritage and technology within the current state of the art. An assessment of launch mass versus launch energy for the three opportunities was used. A parametric assessment of the MAV was made based on an extensive database of aerospace technology, linking standard, aerospace engineering tools. The TRL of actual components that can be used in the MAV is high. Some elements are currently in use for DoD applications. The Earth Return Vehicle (ERV), the element that drives overall mission performance, was scrutinized by two separate approaches. A parametric approach, similar to that used for the MAV was compared to a “bottoms up” design using COTS components. The MAV plus ERV stack was optimized over several iterations and convergence was achieved. Supporting mission equipment such as the sample collection and transfer system and internal structures were conceptually designed to yield a sensible comprehensive understanding of the system. The critical Entry Descent and Landing (EDL) portion, performed propulsively by Red Dragon, using a lifting trajectory with bank angle modulation, was examined and is described in a forthcoming paper [8].

Mass rollups for all elements of the selected family of options produce an architecture that closes using storable propellant for the MAV.

As a means to sample the alternative architectural space, other options such as Earth Direct Entry (EDE) and Mars in-situ resource utilization (ISRU) were concurrently studied. We identified important PP Back Contamination issues that bear on the selection of options for final delivery of the sample to Earth. We also identified separate Forward Contamination issues for Mars landing and operations. Although mass savings can be achieved by using ISRU, power requirements and development lead time for the ISRU processing equipment are both high. For the EDE case, an EEV similar to that used in the MSR Orbiter Mission study3 is too massive and requires additional development work.

4. ARCHITECTURE ELEMENT DESCRIPTION

The major hardware items required for the MSR mission are described in this section and include an integration of hardware derived from emerging commercial capabilities; maturation of small spacecraft design techniques; new utilizations of traditional aerospace technologies, and the application of recent technological developments. Also described in this section are the EDL approach; options and approaches for the ERV; propellant options for the MAV; and interfaces to the Mars 2020 Rover mission.

Falcon Heavy

The Launch vehicle for the Red Dragon MSR mission will be the Falcon Heavy, currently under development by SpaceX. Performance of the Falcon Heavy has been derived by Tito, et al [9] and is shown in Figure 2. The first flight of the Falcon Heavy has not yet occurred, however, SpaceX has made steady progress in the development of their Falcon 9 line. The Falcon Heavy Launch Vehicle is an example of an emerging commercial capability. Earth Launch mass is less than 11 mt, which is within the estimated capability of a Falcon Heavy, for launch opportunities in 2022, 2024, and 2026. The highest C3 of 13.2 km²/sec², for the preferred 2022 opportunity, was used in the analysis. The C3 for the

2026 opportunity is significantly less. Launch margins vary between 22% and 27%. A representation of the launch mass is shown in Figure 3.

Red Dragon Capsule

The Red Dragon capsule will be a modified version of the Dragon capsule currently in service as a cargo re-supply and return vehicle. Dragon will be upgraded by SpaceX to carry crew and eventually perform ground landings. The Dragon capsule is another example of an emerging commercial capability. Two of the SpaceX upgrades are applicable to the MSR mission: 1) Addition of Super Draco thrusters for launch abort and possible ground landing assist. 2) Landing legs for ground landing. It is anticipated that these legs will extend through ports in the Dragon heat shield.

There will have to be additional modifications to the standard Dragon capsule in order for it to become a Red Dragon suitable for MSR. Important modifications are listed in Table 1.

EDL Approach

The analysis of the EDL approach for Red Dragon, included a determination of propellant mass fractions for entry, terminal descent, and hazard avoidance. The propellant

Figure 2. Derived Falcon Heavy Launch Performance [9]

Figure 3. MSR Launch Mass Representation

Table 1. Red Dragon MSR Modifications

No.	MODIFICATION ITEMS
1	Interior modifications to the Dragon to incorporate and structurally support the MAV within a launch tube will be required. It is anticipated that attachments to existing hard points can be made, as shown in Figure 4. A complete structural evaluation will also need to be made, however, comparing anticipated MSR loads to load cases required for human rating lends confidence in the capability of Red Dragon to perform the MSR mission.
2	Additional tanks will be required to carry the propellant required for the complete EDL process, including terminal descent and hazard avoidance. A possible tank arrangement scheme is shown in Figure 5.
3	An exhaust venting scheme will need to be incorporated into Red Dragon. Several possibilities were investigated. One option is the utilization of existing hatch and window openings that requires complex ducting. Another option is a “missile silo” type vertical vent annulus that requires turning vanes at the base of the MAV. A more direct approach utilizes a port or hatch in the heat shield, directly below the MAV, as shown in Figure 6 was selected. Entry heating is low and it has been mentioned that landing leg ports will be introduced by SpaceX. There is also precedent for heat shield hatches, from such items as Space Shuttle landing gear and umbilical doors.
4	A robotic arm will be installed along with a mechanism for opening the Red Dragon side hatch. These mechanisms will be required to obtain a contingency sample as well as to transfer the sample container from the rover to the ERV at the top of Red Dragon.

Figure 4. MAV Mounted in Red Dragon

Figure 5. EDL Propellant Tank Arrangement

quantity will require mission unique tanks as shown in Figure 5. An assessment of the effect of the entry conditions on the thermal protection system (TPS), currently in use for Dragon missions, has also been performed and indicated a non-stressing condition. Details of the EDL approach are described in a forthcoming paper [8] and are summarized here. The Red Dragon will utilize a lifting trajectory, combined with bank angle modulation in order to fly the entry and landing trajectory until the point that retro propulsion can be utilized. The Super Draco thrusters will perform the final braking, terminal landing, and hazard

avoidance. No parachutes are utilized in this approach. This is an example of an application of recent technological developments. Total entry masses between 7 and 10 mt were considered with closure occurring between 9 and 10 mt. The entry mass accounts for all of the elements needed to perform the MSR mission, including the Red Dragon capsule, MAV, the ERV, mission unique support equipment, and the total propellant to perform the entry and landing operations. A useful payload of 2 mt is provided and includes the MAV, ERV, and support equipment. A representation of the useful mass is shown in Figure 7

MAV exhaust vents through heat shield port

Figure 6. MAV Exhaust Venting Approach

Figure 7. Red Dragon Useful Mass Representation

Earth Return Vehicle and Retrieval Options

The ERV balances the architecture since its mass travels the farthest, including a decent to and ascent from Mars; therefore the ERV is worthy of a significant amount of design consideration. In addition, the ERV is a strong candidate for the application of maturing small spacecraft techniques. In the baseline MSR architecture, the ERV has several functions.

The ERV receives a the sample from a rover, and after it is launched into a temporary phasing orbit, injects into a cruise towards Earth. Once near Earth the ERV performs Earth and lunar swing-bys and enters into a, Lunar Trailing Orbit (LTO). A later mission, retrieves the sample container as shown in Figure 8. In this approach, a Dragon or Orion capsule, operated by a crew or robotically, performs a rendezvous with the ERV and uses an arm to transfer the sample container from the ERV to a sealed volume in the nose of the capsule. The capsule then performs an Earth re-entry. In this baseline, the ERV propulsion system includes standard MON3 and pump-fed main thrusters. ERV alternatives are listed in Table 2.

After assessing the possible alternatives, no conclusive decision was reached for option 1 in Table 2. Options 2 and 3 in Table 2 are now considered part of the baseline. The inclusions of advanced technologies, shown in Table 2 was

considered via trades between benefits and penalties. Option 4 was rejected since NOFB has not yet been flight tested. Option 5 has not yet been accepted within the baseline due to the high mass of the EEV. An effort to significantly lighten the EEV, as future work described in Section VII, may allow EDE to be reconsidered along with PP Policy implications associated with sample container handling.

Figure 8. LTO Sample Retrieval

During the early portion of the MSR study the ERV mass was defined by a coupled set of Mass Estimation Relationships (MERs). Such a parametric approach treats the masses (and sometimes volumes) of all the significant subsystems (thrusters, tanks, structure, etc.) as idealized, analytic functions. The MERs predict the mass of a future system based on an historical database of previous systems of an analogous nature. The original baseline described earlier and a ΔV budget distribution is as presented in Table 3. The budget giving the highest total, for the 2026 opportunity, was used. The total for the preferred 2022 opportunity is slightly less. By combining the highest C3 value, as described in the Falcon Heavy discussion earlier, with the highest, although non-concurrent 2026 ΔV budget conservatism is added to the analysis. ΔV reserves for ascent propellants and the ERV trajectory are also provided. The parametric design mass budget for the ERV is summarized in Table 4.

Give the critical balancing nature of the ERV, a later, bottoms-up estimate was performed using actual COTS components to meet performance requirements. This bottoms-up approach utilized alternative options 2 and 3, described in Table 2. The bottoms-up MEL is shown in Table 5. Option 5, EDE as described in Table 2, is not

Table 2. ERV Options

No.	ERV OPTION ITEMS
1	The retrieving spacecraft can be either a crewed or robotic mission, using spacecraft under development such as a Dragon or Orion capsule. An arm is used to bring the sample into a sealed chamber within the capsule which will return to Earth. In this study, both options were defined, however, no conclusive choice has been made. Robotic operations are inherently less expensive. On the other hand, the expense of the crewed option provides contingency capability as well as an opportunity to operate in cis-lunar space.
2	The propulsion system for the ERV can include a set of tanks that can be jettisoned, in a 1 and ½ stage approach.
3	Main thrusters can be pressure-fed to reduce development risks associated with small engines that require the multiple burns shown in Table 3.
4	Use Nitrous Oxide Fuel Blend (NOFB) rather than propellant with MON3 oxidizer in a pressure-fed configuration. NOFB is a single part blend of fuel and oxidizer. Propulsion system mass savings are possible due to the reduction in the number of tanks and amount of plumbing. NOFB can be transported and handled without undue precautions or hazards. NOFB has not yet been space tested.
5	Instead of operations in LTO, the ERV will deploy an Earth Entry Vehicle (EEV) that carries the sample in an Earth Direct Entry maneuver (EDE). Within the study, this approach was initially modeled as the superposition of the EEV defined in the MSR Orbiter Mission study [3] on the ERV. The use of EDE will eliminate the need for launch and operation of a retrieval spacecraft.

included since it does not provide a closed architecture. A separate breakdown for jettisoned elements, option 2, is provide. By comparing Tables 4 and 5 it can be seen that the bottoms-up mass is slightly greater than the parametric mass but we conclude that the architecture remains closed. The bottoms up design accounts for a sample container design. The mass allocation of 500 g for the sample follows MEPAG guidelines [10].

Mars Ascent Vehicle

The function of the MAV is to launch its payload, the ERV, from the surface of Mars to a temporary phasing orbit. The Mars Ascent vehicle was designed as a single stage to orbit. The initial launch point was 0 m MOLA altitude, 0° Latitude and 0° Longitude. Trajectory heading was due East. The latitude range of the landing / launch site was later expanded to +/- 45 degrees. The MAV was sized for each value of total ΔV and assumed payload mass using a set of assumptions and ground rules. These values were consistent with the results of other portions of the work and were tracked and updated through the course of the study. The ΔV budget distribution for the MAV is presented in Table 6. The assumptions are based on best practices and experience for the conceptual design phase. The results for this portion of the MSR study showed the technical feasibility of a MSR stack consisting of a single stage MAV and with the ERV as its payload. The ERV was described in the previous section. A set of MERs at the subsystem level were developed for

this class of vehicle, and integrated into a vehicle synthesis code for computing mass and volume, and performing vehicle closure to meet mission requirements. These MERs included the expected elements such as structures, power system, propulsion system, nose fairing, thermal insulation, actuation devices, guidance and communication. Best practices and State-of-the-Art and traditional aerospace technologies were used. A dry mass growth allowance of 30% was used.

Preliminary analysis of Red Dragon indicated that the capsule could land up to 2000 kg of useful payload, as broken down in Figure 7, at terrain elevations between -0 and - 4 km MOLA elevation. Available Red Dragon internal volume allocated to the MAV and ERV, is approximately 1.2 m diameter and 4+ m length.

A feasible MAV/ERV design has been demonstrated with gross liftoff mass of 1300 kg. The MAV overall body length and diameter are compatible with the Red Dragon. A set of design and trade studies, as listed in Table 7 have been completed using multiple iterations. From these studies a baseline configuration was defined and sensitivity studies about the baseline design were performed. A description of a representative subset of this data is included in Table 8. Full documentation will be available in a forthcoming NASA Technical Memorandum [11]. A combined mass statement for the MAV / ERV stack is provided in Table 9. Overall dimensions are given in Table 10.

Table 3. ERV Design ΔV Budget Distribution

Trajectory Component	ERV ΔV, m/s
Circularization at Mars Phasing Orbit	37
TEI	2114
TEI Gravity Loss	21
Mid-course	75
Earth Fly-by	641
Earth Fly-by Gravity Loss	1
Moon Fly-by	0
Circularization at Earth Lunar Trailing Orbit	25
Disposal to Heliocentric orbit	25
Subtotal	2939
7.2% Reserve	211
Total ΔV	3150

Table 4. ERV Parametric Design Mass Budget

Category	Mass - kg
ERV dry	50
27% mass growth allowance	13.5
Subtotal dry	63.5
Sample container + sampler	8.5
Subtotal dry + container + sample	72
Propellant	133
Total ERV wet as payload to the MAV	205

Table 5. ERV Bottoms Up COTS Design Mass Budget – kg
incl. 30% growth unless noted and incorporates options 2 & 3 from Table 2

Subsystem	Component (units)	Mass	Subsystem	Component (units)	Mass
ADACS	Star Tracker (1)	0.80	Thermal	Coatings (1)	0.13
	IMU (1)	0.98		Heaters (12)	1.40
	Sun Sensor (4)	0.05		MLI (1)	0.04
	RWA (4)	3.6		Temp. Sensors (6)	0.39
C&DH	Integrated Avionics. (1)	6.9		Thermoelectric Cooler (1)	0.13
Power	Battery Pack (3)	6.24		Propulsion	Fixed tank (2)s
	Solar Array (1)	1.59	Jettisoned tanks (2)		9.2
Structure	Dust Cove (1)r	0.91	Fixed valves / filters (2)		2.7
	Fasteners, Hinges, Latches (1)	3.90	Jettisoned valves / filters (2)		2.7
	Cabling (1)	2.60	Main thruster (1)		6.8
	Second. Structure (1)	0.44	Vernier thrusters (6)		3.5
	Prim. Structure. (1)	4.39	Structure (1)		2.0
Telecomm	LGA (2)	0.21	Jettison mechanism (1)	1.3	
	HGA (1)	1.6	Payload	Sample Container – 50% mass growth (1)	4.0
	Transponder, XS (2)	7.8		Sample [10] with 20% mass growth (1)	0.60
	Diplexers (3)	1.4	Subtotal dry	82	
			Propellant	129	
			Total wet	211	

Alternate MAV Propellant Options

The baseline propellant for the MAV is storable hypergolic propellants (NTO / MMH). Designs and trade studies were also conducted for alternate propellant types for the MAV.

These included LOX / RP-1 and LOX / Liquid CH4. For the alternate propellant designs, LOX would be manufactured on Mars, using in-situ resources. The fuel would be brought from Earth, emulating the strategy described in the current Mars Human Reference Mission Architecture [12]. Workable MAV designs were produced and mass savings were achieved; however, even the generous volume of Red Dragon has limits. Red Dragon does not provide enough volume to package the MAV / ERV stack, mission unique support equipment, EDL propellant, and the ISRU equipment. In addition, the TRL of the ISRU process was not deemed sufficiently high enough to support a timely MSR mission implementation.

Table 6. MAV Design ΔV Budget Distribution

Trajectory Component	MAV ΔV , m/s
Orbital	3299
Aero Drag Loss	4.0
Gravity Loss	400
Thrust Vectoring Loss	327
Atmospheric Loss	1.1
Coriolis Loss	0
Inclination Loss (due east from N/S Lat. 45)	70
Subtotal	4101
3.6% Reserve	149
Total ΔV	4250

Table 7. MAV Trade Study Items

No.	MAV TRADE STUDY ITEMS
1	Fore body shape.
2	Propellant tank configuration – intertank space versus nested tanks.
3	Propellant feed – pumped versus pressure..
4	Propellant type – storable versus cryogenic (LOX manufactured on Mars using ISRU techniques).
5	Oxygen / Fuel ratio
6	Number of engines – 1 to 4
7	Engine chamber pressure
8	Engine nozzle expansion ratio
9	Isp sensitivity

Table 8. Representative MAV DATA

No.	MAV DATA ITEMS
1	Design and analysis methods used for each of the technical areas based on Engineering-level MER's derived from historical data for each of the major subsystem.
2	Higher fidelity codes used, as needed, to supplement the engineering methods
3	Aerodynamics and aero-thermodynamics where computed using CBAERO and CART3D.
4	Ascent was optimized with defined aerodynamics and data from The Mars GRAM atmospheric model, using the POST2 trajectory code. Table 6 presents the velocity loss breakdown for the ascent trajectory to 100km X 250km.
5	Aero loss, thrust vectoring loss, and atmospheric loss are all small. .
6	Rocket engine performance predicted using a quasi-one dimensional nozzle flow, for a pumped, engine, including appropriate thermodynamic and chemical performance as adjusted by comparison to a known reference engine.
7	Nested tank configuration was selected to reduce overall vehicle length
8	General arrangement for the baseline MAV configuration and the internal tank design are shown in Figure 9.

Interface to Mars 2020 Rover Mission

The major elements of the Mars 2020 Rover mission are presumed to include the same elements that were part of the current Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission: 1) Atlas V class launch vehicle, 2) Cruise Stage, 3) Entry Aero shell, 4)

Sky Crane, and 5) Rover. Of these elements only the rover has a direct interface with the MSR architecture described in this paper. The rover will be tasked with collecting and caching samples as defined in the Report of the Mars 2020 Science Definition Team [13] (SDT). It is assumed that the sample container will be delivered to Red Dragon by the rover. It is therefore necessary for the Red Dragon MSR

**Table 9. ERV & MAV
Combined Stack Mass Statement**

Category	Mass - kg
MAV dry	106
30% mass growth allowance	32
Subtotal MAV dry	138
ERV wet as payload to the MAV	205
Subtotal MAV dry + ERV wet	343
MAV propellant, including residuals	955
GLOM	1298

**Table 10. ERV & MAV
Overall Dimensions**

Category	Dimension - m
Length	2.80
Diameter	1.02

Figure 9. General MAV Arrangement

mission to be launched soon after the Mars 2020 Rover. The 2022 launch opportunity is feasible.

It will be necessary for Red Dragon to land close to the projected exploration path of the rover, subject to a safe standoff distance, in order to minimize any rover diversion. Red Dragon can land at any of the sites described in the SDT13. The rover will have to be able to drive up to within reach of the arm on Red Dragon. The rover must be able to present the sample container in a manner that can be transferred to the ERV at the top of Red Dragon. This interaction is depicted in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Rover to Red Dragon Sample Transfer

For total mission success of both the Mars 2020 rover mission and a MSR mission preferentially launched in 2022, planning and development must be coordinated starting early in the life cycle of each, mission considering the time lag between the two.

5. PLANETARY PROTECTION POLICY

All missions to Mars—whether one way or round trip – must comply with Planetary Protection policy rooted in the Outer Space Treaty [14]. Policies [7] are updated over time by COSPAR to reflect advances in scientific knowledge, new technologies and practical experiences of space agencies that launch planetary missions. In the United States, Planetary Protection policy is developed and overseen by NASA’s Planetary Protection Office, which issues requirements and directives addressing both forward and backward contamination concerns.

This proposed MSR architecture will be impacted by several PP Policy provisions that span across the various mission elements and include concerns about both forward and backward contamination. The Red Dragon must provide outbound forward contamination controls that meet requirements for pre-launch cleanliness and bio load reduction for flight hardware. Controls to address backward contamination must also be in place. Controls must be provided for the sample container; transfer of the container to the ERV, and a final transfer of the sample container to the retrieving capsule or EEV, as appropriate. Both the

flight hardware that has been on Mars as well as pristine Martian material returned from Mars will have to be contained. These impacts, along with other critical factors, are summarized in Table 11.

Items 5 and 7 will provide the largest PP challenges and methods to address them may drive large portions of the

integrated with other types of techniques derived from traditional and new sources. The Major Findings in Table 12 provide key points. The significance of the work is that it opens the door to the efficient achievement of an important planetary science objective at a lower complexity level and by extension, a potentially lower cost than previously considered.

Table 11. Planetary Protection Considerations for MSR

No.	PLANETARY PROTECTION IMPACT ITEMS
1	The exterior surfaces of Red Dragon will be exposed to the terrestrial environment during processing and launch. These surfaces will also be exposed the space environment while in transit to Mars. The landing legs and exhaust gas venting system, including entrained material, will also require special attention. These considerations will be addressed in determining PP requirements associated with forward contamination controls.
2	The interior surfaces of Red Dragon, including encapsulated and embedded surfaces—as well as retractable legs , MAV, MAV enclosures, and support equipment) will need to comply with appropriate pre-launch PP cleanliness requirements based on the where on the Martian surface it will land and operate..
3	The sample handling robotic arm end effectors used for obtaining grab samples and for the transfer of the sample container from the Martian surface to the ERV, will need to be sterilized. A separate in-space sample transfer arm, if used, will also require attention.
4	The exterior of the sample container delivered by the 2020 rover will be exposed to Mars material and will need to be suitably contained whether LTO or EDE is used.
5	The exterior surfaces of the ERV will be exposed to Mars materials. If the ERV is operated in the LTO mode, it will be disposed to a heliocentric orbit. If the ERV is operated in the EDE mode, it will fly-by the Earth after the EEV is targeted to Earth entry, and remain on its hyperbolic orbit. In neither case will the ERV enter the Earth’s biosphere or impact the moon.
6	The interior surfaces of the EEV, if the EDE mode is used, will be sealed and contained after the sample container is loaded onboard.
7	The exterior surfaces of the EEV, if the EDE mode is used, will have been exposed to Mars. Protecting all of the exterior surfaces, including the sample container loading port, will be problematic.

architecture. For example, the decision to utilize the LTO or the EDE option may result in different PP requirements. As described earlier, LTO requires another Earth centric mission, but EDE requires the development of containment and sample container transfer mechanisms for use on Mars and in space; advanced TPS technology (currently in NASA’s portfolio); and structures technology to ensure that the chain of contact between Mars and Earth is broken.

Figure 8 illustrates both the retrieval and containment strategy for LTO that was studied. For EDE, several notional containment schemes were postulated but not studied in depth. These schemes include coatings and mechanisms for loading the sample container into the EEV. These schemes are not yet mature and will need to be addressed as part an overall EEV study.

6. CONCLUSION AND MAJOR FINDINGS

Summary

An MSR mission in the preferred 2022 opportunity that retrieves samples collected by the Mars 2020 rover is feasible with the use of emerging commercial technologies

Lower Cost Rationale

This paper provided an overview of the results of a study of a new MSR architecture and asserts that such architecture can be less costly than previous MSR proposals. The most recent concept [2 – 4] utilized three Mars missions and over a dozen flight articles with numerous interfaces. The MSR architecture described in this paper utilizes one Mars mission and includes four flight articles and a limited number of interfaces. A formal cost estimate is certainly the next step to be undertaken and is listed in Section 7, Future Work. At the present time, a lower overall cost does seem likely since the technical feasibility of using only one new Mars launch has been established.

It can be argued that the 2020 Mars rover should be counted as another Mars mission, with the rover as a fifth flight article, within this architecture. A fair approach will be to allocate a portion of the 2020 rover mission cost as part of the cost of this MSR architecture. Such items as the cost of mission unique capabilities to interface with Red Dragon and some portion of the cost of a mission extension will need to be determined.

It is also true that the Earth retrieval portion of the architecture, a mission to a Lunar Trailing Orbit (LTO), is another mission, but it is not a mission to Mars. Options for a crewed versus robotic retrieval mission will certainly be a large cost driver, and they need to be fully traded. Such a trade will include costs versus operational benefits. On the other hand, the direct Earth entry approach can eliminate the retrieval mission but carries the cost of advanced, low mass, highly reliable entry vehicle development. A thorough trade will be required for this approach as well.

7. FUTURE WORK

Moving forward, Table 13 shows recommended future work. If this MSR option advances to the point where it is acted upon, initiation of joint mission planning between the Mars 2020 Rover project and this potential MSR project should begin at the earliest possible date.

Table 12. Major Findings Support the Application of Commercial Capabilities for MSR

No.	MAJOR FINDING
1	A minimum-energy transfer to Mars is possible in the preferred 2022 opportunity using a Falcon Heavy capable of throwing ~ 13 mt to Mars. Launch energy requirements for the 2024 and 2026 opportunities are lower, however these opportunities will require longer 2020 rover extensions.
2	EDL using Red Dragon in a lifting trajectory, decelerating aerodynamically and with supersonic retro-propulsion can soft land a vehicle mass of 6,600 kg, including 2,000 kg of useful payload mass, onto the Martian surface.
3	The payload is a fully fueled Earth return launch system capable of launching a small (5 kg) payload directly to Earth. Also included is a sample transfer and storage system with grab sample capability as well as structural supports and exhaust venting to accommodate the launch vehicle. Vehicle health systems are also included.
4	The LTO recovery option can be designed within the ERV mass and volume goals, with confidence and without requiring the infusion of advanced technology. An EDE mission option can be designed within the ERV mass and volume goals, if an EEV probe mass ≤ 20 kg can be achieved. This design goal may be achievable with the infusion of advanced entry systems configurations and TPS currently within NASA's technology development portfolio.
5	Employing propellant tanks that are jettisoned can produce useful mass savings for the ERV, and thus the entire architecture.
6	Employing pressure-fed engines for the ERV reduces development risks associated with small engines that require multiple starts.
7	The ERV along with the LTO and EDE recovery options are high priorities for future study.
8	Planetary Protection policy, as determined by international agreements, will influence sample transfers and sample recovery processes. High reliability requirements are key drivers.
9	The use of ISRU in the same way as described in potential human exploration missions is not feasible within the earliest of the opportunities examined. High volume, high power – requiring a nuclear power plant, and low equipment TRL work against this option.
10	A MSR mission in the preferred 2022 opportunity that retrieve samples collected by the Mars 2020 rover is feasible by integrating emerging commercial capabilities with other existing and new types of capabilities.
11	High performance, pump-fed, high engine thrust-to-engine weight ratio rocket engines are important.
12	Important PP impacts for this MSR mission, have been identified and analyzed..

A mission extension of the Mars 2020 rover will be required to implement this architecture. Mission extensions are recognized as difficult to justify in the current budget climate, however, the potential for emerging commercial capabilities as well as an architecture that is simpler than previous proposals, can offset this difficulty. Underpinning any estimate will be the newer cost paradigms offered by the emerging commercial sources that have begun to develop a performance and cost track record.

Table 13. Recommended Future work

#	FUTURE WORK TASK	TASK SCOPE
1	Mission Cost Estimate and Explore Partnership Opportunities	Determine a realistic engineering cost estimate, and determine partnership opportunities
2	CFD Study of Supersonic Retro-propulsion	Mission specific application of Supersonic Retro Propulsion
3	Earth Return Vehicle design studies – technical elements equivalent to pre ϕ A study.	Define and Document a study that defines a full set of mission and spacecraft requirements and provides a preliminary design using COTS components with appropriate margins and growth allowances.
4	Detailed study of a lighter weight EEV to allow reconsideration of EDE.	Application of current Thermal Protection System technology and addressing containment and high reliability entry and transfer requirements imposed by Planetary Protection Policy[7]. Trade study of EEV development versus the cost of a LTO retrieval mission.
5	Detailed study of Mars Ascent Vehicle (MAV).	Application of current technology from DoD programs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND DISCLAIMER

Acknowledgements

The work described in this paper was performed with funding support from the Ames Center Investment Fund. The contributions of the study team including the following individuals are gratefully acknowledged:

- Steven Hu, Project Management
- Joseph A. Garcia, ERV parametric design
- Cyrus J. Foster, Trajectories
- David Willson, sample transfer on Mars and mechanical engineering
- Michael Soulage, mechanical engineering
- Eddie A. Uribe, Red Dragon internal systems
- Bernardus P. Helvensteijn, ISRU and cryogenics
- Charles J. Hatsell, Red Dragon internal system
- Jeffrey R. Feller, ISRU and cryogenics
- Ali Kashani, ISRU and cryogenics
- Sasha V. Weston, trade studies and engineering research
- John Love, propulsion

We also appreciate management support from:

- Dr. Simon (Pete) Worden
- Dr. Michael D. Bicy
- Dr. George L. Sarver
- Chad R. Frost.

Disclaimer

The work described in this paper was performed internally by NASA’s Ames Research Center using information in the public domain and without the assistance of any commercial organization. There is no endorsement of any particular commercial organization by NASA. There is also no endorsement of this work by any particular commercial organization.

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